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Dissemination Plan - second version

CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD PROJECT

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Executive summary

CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD is an HORIZON 2020 project aiming to build a digital platform that will contribute to improving the quality of life of people living with dementia and their caregivers, considering this “dyad” as the unit of care. The platform will provide value-added services based on social networks, tailored interventions, clinical strategies and gamification, for supporting people living with dementia and their caregivers to live well in the community for as long as possible.

The current report constitutes the second version of the Dissemination Plan (D7.2) of the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD project, elaborated under Task 7.1 “Dissemination & Communication”, within Work Package 7 “Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation and Business Planning”.

This second version of the Dissemination Plan builds on the initial strategy developed in D7.2 and focuses on both the evaluation of the activities implemented during the first half of the project and the dissemination targets for the next period, outlining specific actions and activities expected by the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD consortium members, to ensure communication success and maximum publicity of the project’s results.

More specifically, the content of this updated version of the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD Dissemination Plan incorporates:

- the targeted audiences, namely those who are relevant to and may benefit from project activities;
- the objectives of the dissemination strategy, as well as the defined framework (the communication tools/instruments to reach out to the target groups, the time plan for disseminating the project’s results, the consortium responsibilities and the relevant work packages and milestones);
- an overview of the activities carried out up to month 18 (M18) of the project, along with a relevant assessment based on Key Performance Indicators (KPIs);
- any adaptations needed to the initial Dissemination Plan, following from the experience of the 1st half of the project’s implementation.

Up to this stage (M18), the dissemination strategy put in place has been proven effective, since, with all partners’ contribution, the initially defined activities have been implemented and the objectives set for the 1st half of the project have been achieved. Specifically, the performance on certain dissemination objectives (e.g. web-portal traffic, visibility on social media, impact of project’s events) and the actual quantitative results recorded until M16 (April 2017) show that the initial targets have been met successfully (see Table 1).

Table 1: KPIs monitoring for CAREGIVERPO-MMD dissemination activities

M16 (April 2017)			
Objective Results	Number of web-portal visits	Followers in Social Media	Minimum number of participants in each of the project events
Expected	800	100	40
Actual	5.030	250	75

Besides the successful progress against particular quantitative targets, the project partners have attended and presented CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD in several relevant external events (27 in total), producing also 13 publications in conferences and scientific journals. In addition, two large workshops were organised by the team itself during the first period (up to M18), in order to boost communication of the project around the pilot sites, while another two workshops will follow within the upcoming months, to coincide with the pilots' operation.

Taking into consideration the highly satisfactory performance of the project in terms of dissemination and communication activities, no major changes are foreseen in this deliverable against the initial Dissemination Plan. However, aiming to multiply project's publicity and in view of the pilots' study operation, some adaptations have been implemented regarding the dissemination tools (*i.e.* additional section in the project's website, additional subscription form to the newsletter, YouTube channel, additional promotional material, social media accounts for each pilot site etc.) with the purpose to further foster the dissemination strategy.

List of Acronyms

Acronym	Title
DoA	Description of the Action
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
EC	European Community
EEN	European Enterprise Network
EU	European Union
PLWD	People living with dementia
NCP	National Contact Point
KPI	Key Performance Indicator

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1 Introduction

This report constitutes the second version of the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD Dissemination Plan, introducing the updated dissemination and communication strategy, along with the associated actions that will continue to be implemented throughout the next 18 months of the project. In addition, the report provides an overview of the dissemination activities already performed during the first half of the project, in line with the initial version of the Dissemination Plan (D7.2 delivered in M3)¹.

The main objective of the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD dissemination and communication strategy, as set in the first version of the Dissemination Plan of the project (D7.2), is to create and enhance awareness on the project's activities and results across the defined target groups (see Section 3), thus helping to achieve project's success, in line with the contractual obligations that the consortium has undertaken with the EC.

More specifically, this updated version of the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD Dissemination Plan aims to:

- evaluate the various types of dissemination tools implemented and activities carried out and define future actions;
- define responsibilities among partners;
- summarize the internal monitoring and reporting of dissemination activities, and
- provide an indicative timetable/work planning of promotional activities during the next months of the project.

This second version of the Dissemination Plan is the main document of reference for the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD partners to find information regarding their promotional and communication tasks and responsibilities. It should be noted that the level of impact of all publicity actions described in this document relies on the active participation of all consortium partners.

¹D7.2 <http://caregiversprommd-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/Dissemination-Plan-1st-version.pdf>

2 Management of the Dissemination Plan

The Dissemination Plan is produced by the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Leader (Q-PLAN) under Work Package 7 and is approved by the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD project coordinator (UPC) before submission to the EC. Q-PLAN is responsible for updating or changing the Dissemination Plan, when necessary.

Before a new version is put into force, a draft version is sent out by Q-PLAN to all partners for gathering feedback. Q-PLAN takes into account the comments of the partners, finalizes the new version of the Dissemination Plan and releases the new version, after the approval of the Project Coordinator, UPC.

CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD partners are expected to comply with the Dissemination Plan, so as to identify all dissemination activities they have to carry out and ensure their high quality. Partners are also responsible for adapting the dissemination activities described in this document to their countries (*i.e.* at national level) and for performing effective follow up and reporting of their publicity activities.

According to the DoA, a summary report on CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD events and communication activities will be delivered by the end of the project, in December 2018 (M36), presenting the events and communication activities carried out during the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD grant, as well as providing an overall evaluation of the project's dissemination activity, with specific information for each action.

3 Dissemination target groups

The target groups for project dissemination already identified in the first version of the Dissemination Plan (D7.2), in M3 of the project, are the following:

- Scientific community (including scientists involved in R&D activities related to neurocognitive disorders);
- Dementia and Alzheimer's disease associations and networks (including social media groups, websites and on-line communities);
- Healthcare professionals specializing in neurocognitive disorders;
- Policy makers in the field of health and social care;
- Similar EU collaborative initiatives;
- Potential end-users (people living with dementia, informal caregivers, professional caregivers, professional social workers, dyads of people living with dementia and caregivers, healthcare professionals, *etc.*).

Remark: The direct engagement of potential end-users is a priority for Social Network Services of the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD platform. For this reason, the proposed actions for disseminating project results and enhancing awareness directly among potential end-users are described in detail in D4.5 Social Media Plan. The exact definition and identification of potential end-users is provided in D7.5 Business Plan.

4 Dissemination tools

The implementation of the project's dissemination and communication strategy is based on the employment of a set of instruments, aiming to boost and multiply publicity of the project's aims and achievements. The main dissemination tools used for CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD project are the following, as identified in the initial Dissemination Plan (D7.2):

- project web-portal and partners web-portals,
- project social media accounts (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube) as well as partners' and pilots' social media accounts,
- online newsletter and targeted recipients mailing list,
- Social Media Networks of the platform,
- promotional material (logo, leaflet, poster, presentation, video and promotional material for project events),
- publications in popular and sector press/media (press releases, interviews *etc.*),
- scientific publications,
- participation in external popular events (exhibitions, business events, information days, *etc.*),
- workshops organized at the project's pilot sites,
- participation in scientific events (conferences, *etc.*);
- CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD workshops and training/demonstration sessions,
- CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD closing event;
- synergies with other EU projects/initiatives, and
- EU dissemination channels.

With the exploitation of the abovementioned dissemination tools, the consortium aims to meet the following dissemination objectives:

- Present and promote effectively the project to all possible target groups/audiences in national and European level.
- Establish links with international organizations and other interested stakeholders to achieve wider dissemination.
- Set up liaisons with related European projects throughout H2020 project clustering.
- Validate the project outcomes in order to obtain feedback from expert groups, scientists and interested end-user communities.

4.1 Project web-portal and partners web-portals

The project web-portal (<http://www.caregiversprommd-project.eu>) was launched in M5 of the project (May 2016) and it serves as the main communication conduit of the project (see Figure 1), while it will be available for at least five years after the period of the grant.

The web-portal consists of seven sections which include extensive information and news about the project and its activities (see Figure 2), all the publishable outcomes (e.g. promotional material, scientific documents and project deliverables of public dissemination

level - Figure 3), as well as links to relevant projects/initiatives, the social media accounts of the project and the project partner's webpages.

The web-portal is also equipped with an online contact form, allowing visitors to directly communicate with the portal administrators, namely the Dissemination Leader, (see Figure 4) as well as with an online subscription form to the project's newsletter (see Figure 5). Subscription to the newsletter is also supported by a pop-up window that appears when the visitor accesses the deliverables section and prompts him/her to subscribe to CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD newsletter (see Figure 6).

Figure 1: CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD official project's web-portal

Figure 2: News & Events page on CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD official website

Figure 3: Publishable outcomes on CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD official website

Figure 4: Online contact form for visitors

Figure 5: Subscription to the Newsletter form

Figure 6: Pop-up that prompts the visitor to subscribe to CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD newsletter

As mentioned in the first version of the Dissemination Plan, the web-portal has been equipped with a mass e-mail sender tool for the dissemination of newsletters, press releases, invitations to project events etc., which was initially used in order to prepare and disseminate the first issue of the project's newsletter (in M8 of the project). However, in order for the Dissemination Leader to have access to advanced tracking functionalities and reporting tools, a professional web marketing solution, namely MailChimp², was later employed. Mailchimp is a marketing automation platform allowing to manage long communication lists, while offering advanced monitoring capabilities of the information being disseminated. The MailChimp plugin was integrated in the web portal and was successfully used for the dissemination of the 2nd issue of project's newsletter. The use of this tool is recommended for the forthcoming mass online dissemination activities of the project.

Moreover, a new section on the website was created ("Join the pilot"), aiming to support the piloting phase of the project (see Figure 7). Designed to communicate the pilot study, to reach out to potential pilot users and to keep the public informed about the relevant progress and news, the new website page will contain information on how PLWD and their caregivers can

²https://mailchimp.com/?awid=60433614&awag=31581507257&awad=194298324133&awkw=mailchimp&pid=GAW&source=website&gclid=CMLbifL_ydQCFsax7QoduA4Oag&gclsrc=aw.ds&dclid=CPiPu_L_ydQCFXgw0wodcFEDxg

participate in the pilot operation and it will be regularly updated with news from each pilot site.

Figure 7: "Join the pilot" section on the official project's web-portal

A dedicated link will be also available on the web-portal providing access to demonstrations of the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD platform (after its updated version in M25).

The content of the web-portal is being updated at least once per month. Q-PLAN is responsible for the operation and the update of the project's web-portal while all partners are required to:

- Publish occasionally news of the project to the web-portals of their organizations.
- Contribute to multiply project's visibility by sharing the link of the web-portal through their channels.
- Actively contribute to the content update (e.g. by sharing news and events to post).

In addition, the partners responsible for the pilots' operation should communicate to Q-PLAN news and information regarding the pilot operation, so as the latter to keep the relevant web-portal section regularly updated.

Finally, the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD portal should be cited/mentioned in all publicity material generated by the project consortium.

Table 2 below presents the KPIs for the web-portal and the actual quantitative results until April 2017 (M16 of the project), offering insights for the web-site performance until now, which appears to be significantly higher than initially expected.

Table 2: KPIs Monitoring - Web-portal

Relevant Project Objective: Number of web-portal visits (sessions) - <i>cumulatively</i>				
	M16	M21	M27	M34
Expected	800	1500	5000	10000
Actual	5.030	-	-	-

Data Source: Google Analytics & Web-portal server

4.2 Project social media accounts (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube) and partners social media accounts

A CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD LinkedIn group, a Facebook page and a Twitter account have been created in M1 of the project. The project social media pages have been continuously updated in English, with news about the project’s activities and results, various events, scientific news, news from dementia-related organizations/associations, etc. The frequency of social media posts depends on the availability of news about the activities and results of the project. In any case, a minimum frequency of posts, as described in DoA, serves as a reference point (Facebook – at least two posts per month, Twitter – at least one tweet per week, LinkedIn - at least one post per month) (see Table 3).

From the data presented in Table 3, it seems that the project is very active in Facebook and Twitter. Special care will be given to boost performance of the project’s LinkedIn account during the 2nd half of the project, where tangible results will be available for communication through such a professional social media.

A YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCcv1jQyajkx6yTBo7bvVs1Q>) has also been created to upload CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD promotional videos (see Section 4.4). Other audiovisual material related to the project (e.g. videos from events, interviews, presence in TV) will be also uploaded in the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD YouTube channel.

Table 3: Project’s official social media accounts

Social Media Account	Name	Launched Date	Posts by M18
Facebook	CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD project	January 2016 (M1)	123
Twitter	CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD (@caregiverspromd)	January 2016 (M1)	108
LinkedIn	CAREGIVERSPRO_MMD Project	January 2016 (M1)	11
YouTube	CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD project	June 2017 (M18)	-

Q-PLAN is responsible for the administration of the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD social media accounts and ensures that the interfaces/profiles created, as well as the information published is aligned with the project's objectives and dissemination requirements (*i.e.* concerning logos, funding source acknowledgement, *etc.*).

The project's accounts regularly follow the social media pages of the partners, dementia or Alzheimer's associations and networks, health care structures about dementia or Alzheimer's disease, EU policy makers and similar collaborative initiatives. Moreover, as initially suggested all partners are members or/and followers of the social media pages of the project and keep on promoting them through their personal networks. All partners should continue to interact with news, uploads, tweets and retweets, conversations and "likes" in the social media pages of the project, during the whole three-year duration of the grant, as well as to publish posts/news about CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD regularly on the social media of their organisations. In addition, the project's official social media accounts should interact with the social media networks of the platform, exchanging news, posts, tweets, events *etc.* (see section 4.5).

Table 4 illustrates the KPIs regarding the project's social media networks and the actual quantitative results by M16. The results derived from the first half of the project indicate that the number of followers in social media pages has exceeded the initial expectations, providing evidence for the efficiency of the social media engagement measures put in place.

Table 4: KPIs Monitoring (Social Media Platforms)

Project Objective: Followers/Group members/Friends in project's Social Media platforms (cumulatively)				
	M16	M21	M27	M34
Expected	100	250	1000	3000
Actual	250	-	-	-

Data Source Management: Social Media data & Statistics

4.3 Online newsletter and targeted distribution list

Online newsletter distribution provides the opportunity to increase public and stakeholders' awareness of the project, assists increasing the reachout to the target audience and maintaining contact with it, and encourages readers to find out more about the project, including links to more detailed information on project's website.

Within CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD dissemination activities, an online semester newsletter is regularly distributed among various project stakeholders and the newsletter subscribers. Until M18, two issues of the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD newsletter have already been released, highlighting the main activities of the 1st year of the project (see ANNEX 1), while the third issue is under development.

Each issue is prepared by Q-PLAN, with contribution of the rest of the consortium to the content with articles and news. Newsletter content includes activities and outcomes of the project, news from similar initiatives, news in the relevant scientific fields, *etc.*

For the distribution of the newsletter, the professional web marketing solution MailChimp is used. After its release, the newsletter gets published on the project's official web portal and is further disseminated through the project's social media accounts. Partners are also required to disseminate the newsletter issues through their own dissemination channels. Depending on the amount and importance of news to be presented, the aim is to keep on producing a newsletter at least every 6 months.

The initial distribution list was created and administered by Q-PLAN, based on existing networks and dissemination databases. The rest of the partners also contributed by adding relevant contacts from their own networks. Currently, the list contains 335 subscribers in total, including the newsletter's subscribers and contacts from dementia associations, healthcare researchers, policy makers, similar projects, NCPs, and the EEN-Health sector. The dissemination list will be continuously updated during the whole project's duration, including more relevant contacts that get to know and become interested in the project and newsletter subscribers that register to the list through the web portal. The distribution list may also be used for the ad-hoc dissemination of other news, announcements, *etc.* related to the project activities.

4.4 Promotional material (logo, leaflet, poster, presentation, video and promotional material for project events)

The project promotional material (project logo, leaflet, poster, templates *etc.*) is among the most important tools of the dissemination and communication strategy, since it defines and promotes the project's visual identity.

In this context, the project logo was created under the responsibility of Q-PLAN during the first month of the project, after being approved by all partners (Figure 8). Versions for web and print use are available for all partners in the OpenProject internal project repository. Additionally, a presentation template in PowerPoint (.ppt format), as well as a document/deliverable template in Word (.docx format) were developed for the project's purposes.

Figure 8: Project's logo

In line with the initial Dissemination Plan, a poster and a leaflet (see Figure 9 and Figure 10), presenting general information of the project (aim, objectives, partners, *etc.*), were created in M5 (May 2016) and they are also available on the project's web-portal (<http://caregiversprommd-project.eu/useful-material/>).

Figure 9: Project's Poster

Figure 10: Project's Leaflet

Apart from the general project leaflet and posters, specific printable material for the promotion of CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD events, of training/demonstration sessions and of pilot activities is being prepared when necessary, according to the needs of the partners (see Figure 11, Figure 12 and Figure 13).

Figure 11: Poster for the Italian workshop

Figure 12: Poster for user's recruitment (for the pilot study operation in UK)

Figure 13: Poster for user's recruitment (for the pilot study operation in France)

Promotional material is used both in project workshops and external events where CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD partners participate. All promotional material includes the project logo, the EU flag and the funding source acknowledgement, as required according to the Grant Agreement.

Q-PLAN is responsible for the preparation of the graphic design and content (in English) of all printable promotional material. Each partner is responsible for translation (if considered necessary) and printing according to specific needs. As mentioned in the first Dissemination Plan, **partners should produce no kind of promotional material related to the project without previous review and approval of the WP7 leader, namely Q-PLAN.**

Finally, a short video, of about five minutes duration, presenting CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD project, as well as some short videos demonstrating the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD platform will

be prepared after the release of the updated version of the platform in M25. All videos will be uploaded to the YouTube channel of the project.

4.5 Interaction with social media networks of the platform

In view of the pilot study operation, social media accounts were created for each of the pilot sites, under the Task 4.5 “Social Networks and Communities”, aiming to build community capacity for the pilot operation (see Table 5 and Figure 14). All aspects regarding the operation of the social media networks of the platform for each pilot country (goals, target audience, core topics, editorial calendar, influencer engagement, communication plan, etc.) are presented in D4.5 “Social Media Plan”, that was delivered in M10 (October 2016).

The social media accounts launched for the pilot sites are subject to the official project dissemination guidelines in terms of project identity and include the official logo and name, the EU emblem, as well as an official reference to the funding source.

Table 5: Pilot’s social media accounts

Pilot Site	FB account	Twitter account
UK	CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD project UK	CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD-UK
Italy	Caregiverspro MMD Italia	CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD-IT
France	AidantsPro	CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD-FR
Spain	Cuidadorespro	Cuidadores

Figure 14: Facebook accounts of the pilot sites

Conducive to enhance the visibility of the project, to convey its messages to the target audiences and to communicate the pilot study operation, the interaction between the project’s social media and the platform’s social media should be promoted. Frequent exchange of news, posts and tweets between the social media of the project and those of the

platform should be established, under the responsibility of their respective administrators (Q-PLAN for project’s social media).

4.6 Publications in popular/mass media (press releases, interviews etc.) and scientific publications

Throughout the project lifetime, publications in popular/mass media, as well as scientific publications assist informing the general public, as well as the target audience about the project’s objectives, activities and findings. Scientific knowledge generated during the project is already being shared in open access scientific conferences and journals (see ANNEX 2).

In line with the first version of the Dissemination Plan, all partners are responsible for identifying any publishing opportunities and for carrying out all necessary actions to ensure publication of project assets and conclusions. Each partner will make an effort to publish articles of high quality, which not only reflects on the consortiums’ reputation but also on the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD initiative. All publications must cite or/and refer to the EU contribution and project grant agreement number, as required in Grant Agreement. Examples on how to comply with these requirements can be found in ANNEX 7, along with requirements with regards to scientific publications.

The “CAREGIVERSPRO-Publications.xls” excel sheet is used for keeping track of the project’s scientific publications. The form of the document along with data collected are shown in ANNEX 6.

All partners will keep on producing press and media releases, articles in popular press, material for TV, radio, or other media, etc. on ad-hoc basis during the project, both in English and in local languages.

Table 6, presents the performance indicators for the press releases and the actual quantitative results recorded until M16 of the project (April 2017). The results of M16 meet successfully the initial target set. Moreover, in the time period between M16 and M18 three more press releases have followed.

Table 6: KPIs Monitoring (Press Releases)

Project Objective: Press Releases (cumulatively)				
	M16	M21	M27	M34
Expected	5	10	13	18
Actual	4	-	-	-

NOTE: Having obtained the experience from the 1st half of the project and taking into consideration the very satisfactory performance of the project in terms of dissemination and communication activities, the initial targets concerning press releases set in the proposal stage seem too aggressive for the period after M21 (i.e. M27:20, M34:40). It has been also observed that the impact of press releases is quite lower than the one of the rest dissemination tools employed by the project (online communication tools, events etc.). Therefore, the KPIs for M27 and M34 regarding press releases have been reconsidered, as presented in Table 6.

4.7 Participation in external events (exhibitions, business events, information days, scientific events, conferences, etc.)

Participation in external events such as exhibitions, business events, information days, scientific events and conferences aims to allow the consortium to keep in touch with the latest evolutions in national and international healthcare activities, share knowledge, and establish contact and interactions with key stakeholders/policy and decision makers, while at the same time communicating CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD results.

Throughout the first year of the project, the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD project team participated in a significant number of external events and networking activities related to the knowledge fields of the project (dementia, mild cognitive impairment, Alzheimer's' disease, geriatric medicine, etc.), as well as to EU events related to e-Health (see Table 7 and ANNEX 3). Amongst these events, the partners also attended and presented CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD project in the Mobile World Congress, which is the world's largest gathering for the mobile industry.

Information about the most important relevant activities has also been posted on the project's official website (<http://caregiversprommd-project.eu/news/>), as well as included in the newsletter issues.

Table 7: Participation in external events (status by June 2017-M18)

Type of activity	Number
Participation to a conference	9
Participation to a workshop	7
Participation to an event other than a conference or workshop	9
Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 projects	2

All partners should continue to disseminate CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD project in external events following the respective guidelines (ANNEX 8). They are also highly encouraged to use the project dissemination material (leaflets, posters, presentations, etc). In addition, photos should be taken and communicated to WP7 leader, Q-PLAN, for further dissemination through the project's channels.

Moreover, the "Future Events" list (as part of the "Dissemination list.xls" excel book that can be found in the ANNEX 4), must be continuously monitored and enriched by all partners.

4.8 CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD workshops and training/demonstration sessions

Four workshops including demonstration/training sessions have been planned to be organized in the pilot sites by the responsible partners (COOSS, UHULL, CHU-ROUEN, FUB)

throughout the whole duration of the project. The aim is to familiarize all interested parties with the project and the platform, as well as to collect insights from relevant stakeholders to be fed into the design of the platform.

During the first half of the project, two out of the four workshops were successfully held. The first workshop took place in June 2016 (M6), organized by COOSS, whereas the second was organized by UHULL in January 2017 (M13).

The remaining two workshops (to be organized by CHU-ROUEN and FUB) will follow within the coming months, to coincide with the pilots' operation. Each workshop will be held in the local language and the local dissemination campaigns for the workshops will be under the responsibility of the organizer, with support from Q-PLAN for central level dissemination (project web-portal and social media, newsletter, mass e-mail sender tool for dispatching invitations, press release in English and promotional material in English or local language). Local dissemination campaigns may include: invitations to local media to take part as speakers, TV presence, press releases in local press, *etc.* However, it should be noted again that partners should produce no kind of promotional material related to the event without the previous review and approval of WP7 leader Q-PLAN.

An Event Report is prepared by each partner responsible for organizing a project event, including photos, the list of participants, copies of publications related to the dissemination of the event, *etc.* (ANNEX 9).

Table 8 below presents the performance indicators for the project events and the actual quantitative results recorded up until April 2017 (M16 of the project). The average number of the participants in the project events, as it was recorded up to M16, exceeds the minimum expected.

Table 8: KPIs Monitoring (Events & Workshops)

Project Objective: Minimum number of participants in each of the project events				
	M16	M21	M27	M34
Expected	40	50	50	50
Actual	75	-	-	-

4.9 CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD closing event

By the end of the project, a closing event (possibly as a satellite event at a larger international event, preferably in Brussels) will be organized to present the final results of the project and develop networks for future research. The event will be open to the public and will aim to attract policy makers from several European institutions. The partner responsible for the dissemination and organization of CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD closing event is Q-PLAN. All partners should contribute to further disseminate the final event through their personal networks.

4.10 Synergies with other projects/initiatives

Synergies with other EU-funded or international research projects and initiatives in the relevant research domains are constantly pursued to facilitate knowledge exchange, to gain mutual dissemination benefits and to exploit potential collaborations. Possible synergies include (without being limited to) the following actions:

- inclusion of the project web-portal and social media as links in websites and social media of other projects,
- participation in events of similar projects,
- dissemination of CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD promotional material in events of similar projects,
- invitations to participate in CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD events, and
- exchange of news/invitations/press releases and dissemination through other projects' channels.

In this context, during the first months of the project, the project coordinator (UPC) established contact with the H2020 "ICT4LIFE" project (<http://www.ict4life.eu/>) and it was mutually decided by the two projects to exchange hyperlinks in the official projects' websites and exchange posts and likes in social media. Furthermore, the project coordinator participated in a bilateral meeting with the clinical coordinator of H2020 "m-Resist" project (<http://www.mresist.eu/>), where he had the opportunity to present and promote CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD project.

Moreover, in June 2017, CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD was invited in the workshop "Active ageing, tourism and interdisciplinary/intersectoral approach: good practices and experience" that was carried out within the activities of the 3rd joint seminar organized by the H2020 project "ALTHOUR - Assisted Living technologies for the Health Tourism sector" (H2020-TWINN-2015 – Twinning - <http://alhtour.eu/>). CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD project, and particularly its profiling, personalization and customization approach, was presented by the COOSS team in the session "Best cases from e-Living Cluster".

A "Similar projects and initiatives" list has already been created by Q-PLAN and is part of the "Dissemination_list.xls" excel book (see ANNEX 4). Project partners keep track of all similar projects and initiatives, which might be interested in collaboration, and regularly enrich the list.

4.11 EU dissemination channels

The following EU dissemination channels are going to be used during the project:

- **Health National Contact Points (NCPs) network:** National Contact Points provide guidance, practical information, networking and assistance on all aspects of participation in HORIZON 2020.
- **European Enterprise Network (EEN):** The EEN is an EU network of around 600 business support organisations from more than 60 countries, including chambers of commerce and industry, technology centers, research institutes and development agencies.

- **CORDIS Wire:** CORDIS WIRE is a CORDIS (Community Research and Development Information Service) online service that helps disseminating and promoting EU projects' activities by publishing news and events on CORDIS.
- **EU Info-days/Workshops:** Several communication events organised by EU

The partners have already participated in various events and workshops organised by EU (see Table 9) introducing CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD project, its aims, future steps and activities.

The NCP network and the EEN have already been contacted by the project through the dissemination of the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD newsletters.

The Project Officer may be contacted with regards to possible dissemination activities supported by the EU.

Table 9: Participation to events organized by EU

Title of the event	Date	Place
Infoday: Health, demographic change and wellbeing. H2020-SC1	09/2016	IDIBAPS research institute Barcelona, Spain
EIP-AHA workshop	11/2016	Brussels, Belgium
European Summit on Digital Innovation for Active and Healthy Ageing	12/2016	Brussels, Belgium
Clustering activities with other EU-funded projects (FAIE Project)	05/2017	Ancona, Italy
Presentation of the project to the EIPAHA Group A3 - "Action for Prevention of Functional Decline and Frailty"	06/2017	Ancona, Italy

5 Publicity monitoring

Project partners are expected to continuously carry out publicity actions and also regularly report all publicity and communication outcomes. Q-PLAN is overall responsible for the monitoring and evaluation of the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD dissemination activities.

Reporting of any dissemination activity and publication is required by all partners, by completing the “CAREGIVERSPRO-Dissemination activities.xls” and “CAREGIVERSPRO-Publications.xls” templates (see ANNEX 5 and ANNEX 6) and informing the WP7 leader, Q-PLAN, at the latest three weeks after the activity. Especially for participation in external events, partners should follow the respective guidelines (ANNEX 8). In the case of events organised by the project, the partner responsible for the organisation of the event should prepare an Event Report (ANNEX 9), at the latest three weeks after the dissemination activity or publication.

As already mentioned in previous sections, all publications must cite and refer to the EU contribution and grant agreement number of the project, as required in the Grant Agreement. Furthermore, for ensuring quality and adherence to the dissemination guidelines, partners should produce no kind of promotional material related to the project (e.g. leaflets, press releases, articles to journals) without the previous review and approval of the WP7 leader, Q-PLAN. Examples on how to comply with the EU requirements regarding dissemination can be found in ANNEX 7.

Each project partner should immediately contact Q-PLAN if they identify opportunities, problems or risks arising while planning or implementing publicity actions.

6 Publicity timetable

Table 10 below depicts the timeframe of the several dissemination and communication activities foreseen by the project. The initial timeframe included in D7.2 is still valid and the team adheres to it. The only adaptation implemented is the development of the YouTube account earlier than initially planned, so as to start uploading project videos and other relevant videos before January 2018, since the project’s YouTube presence is expected to significantly facilitate online dissemination of the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD achievements.

Table 10: Timeframe of the dissemination and communication activities of CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD project

Activity	Related Work Packages (WP) and milestones	2016						2017					2018						
		January- February	March- April	May- June	July- August	September- October	November- December	January- February	March-April	May- June	July-August	September- October	November- December	January-February	March- April	May- June	July- August	September- October	November- December
4.1 Web- portal																			
Publicity through project web-portal (Q-PLAN, ALL)	All WPs All milestones																		
4.2 Social media accounts																			
Publicity through Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn (ALL)	All WPs All milestones																		

Publicity through YouTube channel of the project (Q-PLAN)	WP2, WP3, WP5 MS6																		
4.3 Online newsletters																			
Distribution list creation and update (Q-PLAN)	WP7																		
E- newsletter (6 issues) (Q-PLAN, all)	All WPs All milestones																		
4.4 Promotional material																			
Logo (Q-PLAN)	All WPs All milestones																		
Presentation (Q-PLAN)	WP7																		
Leaflet, poster (Q-PLAN)	WP7																		
Video (Q-PLAN, technical partners)	WP2, WP3, WP5 MS6																		
Promotional material for project events (Q-PLAN, organisers of events)	WP7																		
4.5 Publications in popular/mass media and scientific publications																			

Press releases (all)	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6 All milestones																	
Media relations e.g. interviews, articles on CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD in specialized media, mass media etc.(all)	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6 All milestones																	
Scientific publications (all)	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6 MS4, MS5, MS6, MS7, MS8, MS9, MS10																	
4.5 Interaction with Social Media Networks of the platform																		
Exchange of news, posts and tweets between social media of the project and of the platform	All WPs All milestones																	
4.6 Participation in external events																		
Exhibitions, business events, information days (all)	WP7																	
Scientific events, conferences etc. (all)	WP7																	

4.7 CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD workshops and training/demonstration sessions																			
Project workshops (COOS, FUB, CHU-ROUEN, UHULL)	WP4, WP5, WP7 MS3, MS4, MS5, MS6																		
4.8 CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD closing event																			
Project final event (Q-PLAN)	All WPs MS7, MS8, MS9																		
4.9 Synergies with other projects/initiatives																			
Inclusion of links in other projects' webportals, participation in other projects' events, invitations to participate in CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD events, co-dissemination, exchange of news (Q-PLAN, all)	WP7																		
4.10 EU dissemination channels																			
NCPs network, EEN network, Cordis Wire, EU info-days/workshops (Q-PLAN)	WP7																		

7 Conclusions

The current document constitutes the second version of the Dissemination Plan of the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD project. It has been developed by Q-PLAN under the Task 7.1 “Dissemination & Communication” of Work Package 7 “Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation and Business Planning”.

With reference to the initial plan elaborated in D7.2, this deliverable describes the objectives and the defined framework of CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD project’s dissemination strategy, along with an overview of the activities carried out up to M18 of the project. Moreover, it provides an update of the planned dissemination activities and foreseen channels, following the experience of the 1st half of the project’s implementation.

Up to this stage of the project, the consortium has been very active in the dissemination and communication domain and the results by M18 (June 2017) prove that the first Dissemination Plan has been closely followed and implemented, while the objectives initially set have been achieved. All partners contributed to the employment of the project’s dissemination tools, in order to promote effectively the project to all possible target groups/audiences in national and European level.

In particular, the entire consortium assisted in informing the general public and the target audience about the project’s objectives, activities, findings and next steps, through the exploitation of the project’s website and social media, the distribution of newsletters and press releases, the production of scientific publications (13 in total), the participation in many external events (*i.e.* conferences, workshops etc. – 27 in total), as well as the organisation of workshops.

In view of the 2nd half of the project’s implementation and the pilot’s study operation, this second version of the Dissemination Plan introduced some further adaptations, in order to boost the communication strategy of the project. Specifically, the implemented adaptations included the following actions:

- adjustment of the project’s website sections to facilitate user recruitment, promotion of the pilot phase and stakeholder engagement;
- use of a professional web marketing solution for the newsletter’s distribution, to enhance impact tracking capabilities;
- development of additional promotional material, dedicated to the pilot activities;
- design of a YouTube channel for the project and launch of social media accounts tailored to the pilot sites.

The aforementioned actions facilitate fine-tuning of the dissemination strategy to the needs of the second half of the project and are expected to further increase the reach out to the target audience, as well as the general public awareness about CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD project.

To conclude, all partners should keep on actively contributing to the dissemination activities through the exploitation of the defined dissemination tools and channels, promoting and multiplying publicity of the project’s aims and achievements and disseminating targeted messages to all relevant stakeholders. All the relevant activity of the consortium will be

summarised in a final report that will be delivered by the end of the project, in December 2018 (M36).

ANNEX 1 - Newsletter's published Issues

Figure 15 and Figure 16 below, presents the 1st and 2nd issue of CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD newsletter, published in July 2016 and in February 2017 respectively.

Figure 15: Partial view of 1st Issue of CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD newsletter (July 2016)

Figure 16: Partial view of 2nd Issue of CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD newsletter (February 2017)

ANNEX 2 – Project’s publications in scientific journals and conferences

Table 11 below depicts the project’s publications in scientific journals and conferences up until June 2017 (M18 of the project).

Table 11: Project’s publications in scientific journals and conferences (status by M18)

a/a	Type of publication	Title	Partner	Date of publication
1	Peer reviewed publication	CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD: community services, helping patients with dementia and caregivers connect with others for evaluation, support and to improve the care experience.	UPC, MobilesDynamics	2017
2	Peer reviewed publication	Agents as social actors: integrating a Multi-Agent System to mediate in a social network for elder population	UPC	submitted
3	Peer reviewed publication	How Gamification works for Health Behavior Change Support Systems: A Systematic Review	CERTH	submitted
4	Peer reviewed publication	Language as a marker in subjective memory complaints screening: A sensitivity and specificity report	CERTH	submitted
5	Peer reviewed publication	Web-based interventions for caregivers of people with dementia: A systematic review of the factors influencing their effectiveness	UHULL	submitted
6	Peer reviewed publication	Evaluating the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD platform for supporting people with memory problems and caregivers: A usability study	UHULL, FUB, COOSS, UPC, CERTH, CH-RUEN	in progress
7	Paper in proceedings of a conference/workshop	CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD: A European platform to support people living with dementia and their caregivers	UHULL	2016
8	Paper in proceedings of a conference/workshop	Effectiveness of technology-based interventions for People with Dementia (PwD)	UHULL	2016
9	Paper in proceedings of a conference/workshop	Consulting end-users in the design and usability of CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD: An internet based support tool designed for people with dementia and their caregivers	UHULL	2016

10	Paper in proceedings of a conference/workshop	The effectiveness of web-based interventions on dementia caregivers	UHULL	Published in 2016
11	Paper in proceedings of a conference/workshop	Usability study of a web-based intervention to support people living with dementia (PLWD) and their caregivers	UHULL	Published in 2017
12	Paper in proceedings of a conference/workshop	Developing a web-based platform for people living with dementia and their caregivers: A user-participatory study	UHULL	Published in 2017
13	Paper in proceedings of a conference/workshop	Evaluation of benefits of the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD platform giving support and assistance to people living with dementia and their primary caregiver	FUB	Published in 2017

ANNEX 3 - Participation in external events

The following Table 12, includes the external events (conferences, workshops, events other than a conference or workshop, activities organised jointly with other H2020 projects) that the project's partners have participated in, up until M18 of the project (June 2017).

Table 12: Partner's participation in external events (status by June 2017-M18)

A/A	Title of the event	Place	Date	Partners
1	Assistive Social Networks for Elders and Caregivers.". Laboratoire Franco-Mexicain d'Informatique et Automatique (LAFMIA)., Universidad de las Americas, Cholula, Mexico	Mexico	13/01/2016	UPC
2	Assistive Social Networks for Elders and Caregivers.". Laboratorio Nacional de Supercómputo del Sureste, Universidad Benemérita Autónoma de Puebla, Puebla, Mexico	Mexico	13/01/2016	UPC
3	Catalan Digital Health Ecosystem - Mobile World Congress	Spain	24/02/2016	UPC
4	Meeting of the Norman Gerontology Society	France	10/06/2016	CHU-ROUEN
5	Expert meeting on assistive technologies and dementia- University of Huddersfield	UK	05-06/07/2016	UHULL
6	InfoDay Challenge 1 H2020 call	Spain	06/09/2016	UPC
7	Salut, canvi demogràfic i benestar. H2020-SC1. Event organized by the EU to promote participation in H2020	Spain	07/09/2016	UPC

8	Alzheimer's Society Memory walk (Humber Bridge)	UK	12/09/2016	UHULL
9	Conference on ICT R&D Health and Social: Presentation of Caregiverspro_MMD platform.	Spain	29/09/2016	FUB
10	36è journées de la Société Française de Gériatrie et de gérontologie	France	23/10/2016	CHU-ROUEN
11	Intermed Annual meeting during 26th Annual Conference of Alzheimer Europe	Denmark	31/10/2016	UHULL
12	26th Annual Conference of Alzheimer Europe	Denmark	31/10 – 02/11/2016	UHULL
13	EIP-AHA workshop	Belgium	15/11/2016	COOSS
14	Building real assistive social networks for elders and caregivers - Innovation and Technology Workshop	Mexico	28/11/2016	UPC
15	Scientific conference of Sociosanitary Foundation of Manresa	Spain	30/11/2016	FUB
16	European Summit on Digital Innovation for Active and Healthy Ageing	Belgium	06-07/12/2016	COOSS
17	Dementia Research event at the University of Bradford	UK	07/12/2016	UHULL
18	Artificial Intelligence for Business	Spain	13/12/2016	UPC
19	Congrès de Unités de Soins Alzheimer (USPALZ)	France	15/12/2016	CHU-ROUEN
20	Digital technology and dementia (University of Hull)	UK	20/12/2016	UHULL

21	10th Panhellenic Conference on Alzheimer's Disease and Related Disorders and 2nd Mediterranean Conference on Neurodegenerative Diseases	Greece	02-05/02/2017	UHULL
22	XXIII National Congress of the Spanish Psychogeriatrics Society jointly with the European Association of Geriatric Psychiatry	Spain	23-25/02/2017	FUB
23	32nd International conference of Alzheimer's Disease International	Japan	26-29/04/2017	UHULL
24	e-week - Les TIC aplicades a la millora de l'ecosistema socio-sanitari al voltant d'una malaltia crònica	Spain	28/04/2017	FUB
25	Clustering activities with other EU-funded projects (FAIE Project)	Italy	May 2017	COOSS
26	Réunion du Réseau Alzheimer	France	08/06/2017	CHU-ROUEN
27	Workshop: Active ageing, tourism and interdisciplinary/intersectoral approach: good practices and experience (ALTHOUR H2020 project)	Italy	26-28/06/2017	COOSS

ANNEX 4 - Dissemination list excel book

The snapshots below (Figure 17) present the several tabs of the “Dissemination list” excel book, used by the project team to maintain a list of relevant contacts and events. This list is exploited for disseminating project information (e.g. newsletters, ad-hoc announcements) and supporting the team’s participation in interesting events.

D7.6 Dissemination Plan-second version
CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
Name	Website	Country	Comments	Partner with personal contact				
Dementia partnerships	www.dementiapartnerships.com	UK	Knowledge and news portal for Dementia, supported by National Clinical Director for Dementia, NHS England					
Alzheimer Europe	www.alzheimer-europe.org	Luxembourg	NGO umbrella organisation of 37 Alzheimer associations from 30 countries.					
European Working Group of People with Dementia	http://www.alzheimer-europe.org/Alzheimer-Europe/Who-we-are/European-Working-Group-of-People-with-Dementia/Current-Members		The European Working Group of People with <i>Dementia</i> - EWGPWD - is composed of people with <i>dementia</i> . They work to ensure that the activities, projects and meetings of Alzheimer Europe duly reflect the priorities and views of people with <i>dementia</i> . The group operates independently, with its own Board and agenda of activities. The Chairperson of the EWGPWD also sits on the Board of Alzheimer Europe.					
Alzheimer Austria	http://www.alzheimer-seibsthilfe.at/	Austria	Twitter: @alzheimerAT					
Ligue Nationale Alzheimer Liga	http://www.alzheimer-belgium.be/en/	Belgium	Old website					
Alzheimer Bulgaria	http://alzheimer-bg.org/	Bulgaria	Website in bulgarian					
Foundation Compassion Alzheimer Bulgaria	http://www.alzheimerbulgaria.org/	Bulgaria						
Alzheimer Croatia	http://www.alzheimer.hr/	Croatia						
Cyprus Alzheimer's Association		Cyprus						
Czech Alzheimer's Society	http://www.alzheimer.cz/	Czech Republic						
Alzheimerforeningen	http://www.alzheimer.dk/	Denmark						
Alzheimer Society of Finland (Muistiliitto)	http://www.muistiliitto.fi/en	Finland	Non-profit organization, two local branches and 43 local associations across the country with around 13000 members altogether					
Association France Alzheimer (France Alzheimer et maladies apparentées)	http://www.francealzheimer.org/	France						
Deutsche Alzheimer Gesellschaft	https://www.deutsche-alzheimer.de/	Germany	The DAzG provides information about dementia (especially Alzheimer's disease). It is a self-help organisation, which will improve conditions for people suffering from dementia in Germany.					
Panhellenic Federation of Alzheimer's Disease and Related Disorders	http://www.alzheimer-federation.gr/	Greece	Non-profit organization, consists of 35 linked local associations all over Greece					
The Alzheimer Association of Iceland (FAAS)	http://www.alzheimer.is/	Iceland						
The Alzheimer Society of Ireland	http://www.alzheimer.ie/Home.aspx	Ireland	Leading dementia specific service provider in Ireland, 22 branches, 6 regional offices, 33 day care centres, 28 home care/ support services, 28 carer support groups, 3 social clubs, a respite centre, alzheimer national helpline service, accounts 3000 members					
EMDA- The Alzheimer's Association of Israel	http://www.alz-il.net/ang/186-english-2	Israel						
Federazione Alzheimer Italia	http://www.alzheimer.it/	Italy						
Alzheimer Unity Roma Onlus	http://www.alzheimerunity.it	Italy						
Jersey Alzheimer's Association	http://www.jerseyalzheimers.com/	USA						
Association Luxembourg Alzheimer	http://www.alzheimer.lu/	Luxembourg						
Malta Dementia Society	https://sites.google.com/site/maltheadementiasociety/	Malta						
Association Monégasque pour la recherche sur la maladie d'Alzheimer	http://ampa-monaco.com/fr/	Monaco						
Alzheimer Nederland	http://www.alzheimer-nederland.nl/	Netherlands						
Nasjonalforeningen for folkhelsen	http://nasjonalforeningen.no/	Norway						
Polskie Stowarzyszenie Pomocy Osobom z Chorobą Alzheimera	http://www.alzheimer-waw.pl/	Poland						

	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T
	Date	Venue	Organizer	Link															
1																			
2	21-24 April 2016	Budapest	ADI	http://www.adi2016.org/															
3	24-28 July 2016	Toronto, Canada		https://www.alz.org/aaic/about/practical-information.asp															
4	29/9-1/10	London, UK		http://alzheimers-dementia.conferenceseries.com/call-for-abstracts.php															
5	5-7 October 2016	Lisbon		http://www.eugms.org/2016.html															
6	31 October- 2 November 2016	Copenhagen																	
7	10 December 2015	Paris	Association Française des aidants																
8	3-6/9/2015	Gothenburg, Sweden	Swedish Family Care Competence Centre, Carers Sweden, Carers UK	https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/events/6th-international-carers-conference-care-and-caring-future-proofing-the-new-demographics															
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D7.6 Dissemination Plan-second version
CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
	Name	website	Country	Partner with personal contact	Comments				
1	Care Alliance Ireland	http://www.carealliance.ie/funding	Ireland	Care Alliance Ireland is the National Network of Voluntary Organisations supporting Family Carers. Our vision is that the role of Family Carers is fully recognised and valued by society in Ireland.					
2	IACO- International alliance of carer organizations	http://www.internationalcarers.org/	USA	A group of national and multinational non-governmental organizations have created a new international organization to investigate and address issues of international family caregiving with the intent of increasing public awareness of the needs of the family caregiver on a global scale. Incorporated in 2012, the International Alliance of Carer Organizations (IACO) serves as an umbrella organization that provides cohesive direction, facilitates information sharing, and actively advocates for carers at an international level.					
3	Eurocarers-European Association Working for Carers	http://www.eurocarers.org/	Luxembourg	Eurocarers was officially incorporated in Luxembourg in December 2006. The origin of Eurocarers lies in two European networks: Carmen, a network on Integrated care and Eurofamcare a research network on carers of older persons. In the Carmen project researchers, practitioners and policy makers, among them representatives of the carers movement, found each other and came to the conclusion that it was time for carers to be heard at European level. The Eurofamcare network consisting of researchers who mapped the situation of carers of older persons and the policy measures developed for this category in the entire EU and who did quantitative research on the support of carers of older persons in 6 countries - also diagnosed a strong need for carers to make themselves heard in Europe.					
4									
5	Carers UK	www.carersuk.org	UK						
6		www.dementiacarer.net							
7	STADA Arzneimittel	www.stada.com	Germany	publicly traded, international company with a focus on the healthcare market					
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10									
11									
12									
13									
14									
15									
16									

	A	B	C	D	E
	Name	website	Country	Partner with personal contact	Comments
1	University of Liverpool, Ageing research	https://www.liverpool.ac.uk/ageing-research/	UK	Research is focused on biological, medical, psychological and social aspects of ageing. The University fosters interdisciplinary collaborations to help understand the process of ageing as well as help improve the quality of life of a growing elderly population by preventing or delaying the onset of physical or mental decline	
2	Age Institute	http://www.ikainstituutti.fi/in+english/	Finland	The Age Institute studies the everyday lives of older adults, develops services for older people, produces new innovations for older adults and their families, disseminates information about the results of new studies, offers training to professionals, and participates in current discussion on age related issues, values and attitudes. Research topics: physical exercise, functional capacity and health, encounter, inclusion and mental well-being	
3	Centre for Healthy Aging (CEHA)-University of Copenhagen	http://healthyaging.ku.dk/	Denmark	The CEHA is focused on aging research for the advance of better health and reduced frailty. The center involves five research programs: - Molecular Aging and neurobiology - Skeletal Muscle Metabolism - Body and Life - Society and Culture - Health Promotion and Innovation	
4	Danish Centre for Molecular Gerontology (DCMG)- University of Aarhus	http://www.dcmg.dk/index.html	Denmark	The aims of the DCMG are to identify molecular and cellular mechanisms involved in the ageing process and in the origin of age-related diseases, to search for effective means of reducing age-related loss in cellular functions, to search for methods for recovery of lost biological activity during ageing, and to employ the knowledge obtained to prevent some of the age-related diseases. International centre with participating laboratories in Aarhus, Vejle, and Baltimore, USA. Research topics: DNA damage Premature ageing syndromes Alzheimer's and Parkinson's disease Telomeric-regulation of cellular ageing Gene expression and function with ageing Hormesis	
5	Centre for Geriatric Medicine and Gerontology (ZGGF)- Medical School, University of Freiburg	https://www.uniklinik-freiburg.de/zggf.html	Germany	The ZGGF is a centre of excellence for the diagnosis and treatment of memory disorders. It provides diagnostic services and takes part in research of dementia. Research topics: Image analysis of the disordered brain	

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
1	Name	website	Country	Partner with personal contact								
2	Social Policy and Ageing Research Centre (SPARC)- Trinity College Dublin- University of Dublin	http://sparc.tcd.ie/index.php	Ireland	SPARC views on research into the social policy impacts and implications of ageing and generates policy advice and insights that can in turn be used by policy makers and practitioners to improve the lives of older people. Research topics: Participation and inclusion of older people - service delivery to community-dwelling older people, analysis of advocacy in long-stay care settings, social engagement and networks of older adults, participation in hospital discharge, subjective experience of dementia Long-term care - analysis of domiciliary care policies and cash-for-care programmes, study of the social and nutritional aspects of community meals provision and utilisation, policy discourse surrounding ageing-related care Older adults interacting with other age and population groups - contributions of older adults in areas such as childcare and voluntary work, study of migrant workers in the elder care sectors								
3	European Union Geriatric Medicine Society (EUGMS)	http://www.eugms.org/home.html	Belgium	The mission of EUGMS is to develop geriatric medicine in the European Union as an independent specialty caring for all older people with age-related disease, to support that these services become available, to promote education and continuing professional development, to promote geriatric medicine to the European Commission and Parliament, and to promote evidence-based guidelines for the most efficacious preventive and treatment strategies for older people in the European Union. Publishes the European Geriatric Medicine Journal								
4	European Innovation Partnership on Active and Healthy Ageing	http://ec.europa.eu/research/innovation-union/index_en.cfm?section=active-healthy-ageing										
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1										
2	STAR	http://www.startraining.eu/index.php?lang=en								
3	Caring for me and you: A toolkit for carers of people with dementia	https://www.alzheimers.org.uk/caringformeandyou		This project is being generously supported by Nominet Trust and the Stavros Niarchos Foundation.						
4	RAMCIP: Robotic assistance for MCI patients at home	http://www.ramcip-project.eu/ramcip/	CERTH							
5	InLife	http://www.inlife-project.eu	CERTH							
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1					
2	Dementia Adventure	https://www.linkedin.com/company/2059593?trk=tyah&trkInfo=clickedVertical%3Acompany%2CclickedEntityId%3A2059593%2Cidx%3A2-2-3%2CtarId%3A1453283440616%2Ctas%3Adementia	We are a Community Interest Company established to provide short breaks & adventure travel for people with dementia and their carers. We also aim to support others to do the same by offering training courses & consultancy services which link to research projects all with nature in mind.		
3	Alzheimer's and Dementia Professionals	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/1945739/profile			
4	Alzheimer's and Dementia Topics	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/126335/profile	By Alzheimer's Association		
5	Dementia practical advice	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/8160611/profile			
6	Alzheimer's Dementia Support	https://www.linkedin.com/company/5096910?trk=tyah&trkInfo=clickedVertical%3Ashowcase%2CclickedEntityId%3A5096910%2Cidx%3A4-1-11%2CtarId%3A1453283440616%2Ctas%3Adementia			
7	Dementia Care Specialists	https://www.linkedin.com/company/3673977?trk=tyah&trkInfo=clickedVertical%3Ashowcase%2CclickedEntityId%3A3673977%2Cidx%3A4-2-12%2CtarId%3A1453283440616%2Ctas%3Adementia			
8	Dementia Collaborative Research Centres	https://www.linkedin.com/in/dementia?authType=NAME_SEARCH&authToken=Q0zE8loca=en_US&trk=tyah&trkInfo=clickedVertical%3Amynetwork%2CclickedEntityId%3A252726912%2CauthType%3ANAME_SEARCH%2Cidx%3A5-1-13%2CtarId%3A1453283440616%2Ctas%3Adementia			
9	Alzheimer Netherland	https://www.linkedin.com/company/867234?trk=tyah&trkInfo=clickedVertical%3Acompany%2CclickedEntityId%3A867234%2Cidx%3A2-1-2%2CtarId%3A1453283469934%2Ctas%3Aalzheimer			
10	Alzheimer Scotland	https://www.linkedin.com/company/845464?trk=tyah&trkInfo=clickedVertical%3Acompany%2CclickedEntityId%3A845464%2Cidx%3A2-2-3%2CtarId%3A1453283469934%2Ctas%3Aalzheimer			
11	Alzheimer Society London Middlesex	https://www.linkedin.com/company/978059?trk=tyah&trkInfo=clickedVertical%3Acompany%2CclickedEntityId%3A978059%2Cidx%3A2-5-6%2CtarId%3A1453283469934%2Ctas%3Aalzheimer			
12	Alzheimer Society of Ireland	https://www.linkedin.com/company/10219263?trk=tyah&trkInfo=clickedVertical%3Ashowcase%2CclickedEntityId%3A10219263%2Cidx%3A4-1-11%2CtarId%3A1453283469934%2Ctas%3Aalzheimer			
13	Alzheimer Universal	https://www.linkedin.com/in/alzheimer?authType=NAME_SEARCH&authToken=kb31&loca=en_US&trk=tyah&trkInfo=clickedVertical%3Amynetwork%2CclickedEntityId%3A61600788%2CauthType%3ANAME_SEARCH%2Cidx%3A5-1-13%2CtarId%3A1453283469934%2Ctas%3Aalzheimer			
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CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD

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1	Organization	website	Country	Name				
2	FFG - Austrian Research Promotion Agency	http://www.ffg.at	Austria	Astrid Hoebertz	astrid.hoebertz@ffg.at			
3	Union Wallonne des Entreprises	http://www.ncpwallonie.be	Belgium	Mr François Louesse	francois.louesse@ncpwallonie.be			
4	The Brussels Enterprise Agency (Impulse Brussels)	http://www.ncpbrussels.be	Belgium	Ms Sarah Van Haelst	svh@impulse.irisnet.be			
5	Belgian Science Policy Office (BELSPO) - EUROFED	http://eurofed.stis.belspo.be/	Belgium	Ms Pascale Van Dinter	pascale.vandinter@stis.belspo.be			
6	Agency for Innovation by Science and Technology (IWT)	http://www.iwt.be	Belgium	Mr Alain Deleener	adl@iwt.be			
7	Medical University - Varna		Bulgaria	Ms Slava Penova	slava.penova@mu-varna.bg			
8	Medical University - Sofia		Bulgaria	Chief Assist Prof, PhD, MD Evgeni Zhivkov	ejiwkov2000@yahoo.com			
9	Agency for Mobility and EU Programmes	http://www.mobilnost.hr/	Croatia	Ms Branka Bernard	branka.bernard@mobilnost.hr			
10	Research Promotion Foundation	http://www.research.org.cy/	Cyprus	Ms Georgia Kleanthous	gkleanthous@research.org.cy			
11	Technology centre ASCR	http://www.tc.cz/	Czech Republic	Doc, RNDr, CSc Judita Kinkorová	kinkorova@tc.cz			
12	Danisch Ministry of Science, Innovation and Higher Education. Agency for Science, Technology and Innovation		Denmark	Mr Kim Kryger	klk@fi.dk			
13	Estonian Research Council	http://www.etag.ee	Estonia	Mr Argo Soon	argo.soon@etag.ee			
14	Academy of Finland	http://www.aka.fi/eng	Finland	Mr Antti Hautaniemi	antti.hautaniemi@aka.fi			
15	Tekes	http://www.tekes.fi/en	Finland	Ms Katrina Kippo	katrina.kippo@tekes.fi			
16	Institut Pasteur	http://www.pasteur.fr/fr	France	Mr. David ITIER	david.itier@pasteur.fr			
17	INSERM - Institut National de la Santé et de la Recherche Médicale	http://www.inserm.fr/	France	Mr. Nacer Boubenna	nacer.boubenna@inserm.fr			
18	CNRS - Centre national de recherche scientifique	http://www.ceea.fr/	France	Mrs Virginia Sivan	virginie.sivan@cea.fr			
19	CNRS - Centre national de recherche scientifique	http://www.protiavalor.com/site/fr/contrats_eu	France	Mrs Véra Frassetto	vera.frassetto@cnrs-dlr.fr			
20	Université d'Aix Marseille	http://www.protiavalor.com/site/fr/contrats_eu	France	Mrs Céline Damon	celine.damon@univ-amu.fr			
21	BPI France Financement	http://www.bpifrance.fr/	France	Mrs Marielle Mailhes	marielle.mailhes@bpifrance.fr			
22	INSERM - Institut National de la Santé et de la Recherche Médicale	http://www.inserm.fr/	France	Mr Nacer Boubenna	pcn-fet@recherche.gouv.fr			
23	MENESR - Ministère de l'éducation nationale, de l'enseignement supérieur et de la recherche	http://www.enseignementsup-recherche.gouv.fr	France	Mr Guillaume Fusai	guillaume.fusai@recherche.gouv.fr			
24	Project Management Juelich (PtJ)	http://www.nks-lebenswissenschaften.de/	Germany	Dr. Michaela Pöter	m.poeter@fz-juelich.de			
25	PT-DLR	http://www.nks-lebenswissenschaften.de/	Germany	Dr. Lydia Kammler	lydia.kammler@dlr.de			
26	PT-DLR	http://www.nks-lebenswissenschaften.de/	Germany	Dr. Rebecca Breuer	rebecca.breuer@dlr.de			
27	Project Management Juelich (PtJ)	http://www.nks-lebenswissenschaften.de	Germany	Katerina Kotzia	k.kotzia@fz-juelich.de			
28	Project Management Juelich (PtJ)	http://www.nks-lebenswissenschaften.de/	Germany	Dr. Alexandros Theodoridis	a.theodoridis@fz-juelich.de			
29	PT-DLR	http://www.nks-lebenswissenschaften.de/	Germany	Dr. Marit Ackermann	Marit.Ackermann@dlr.de			
30	Forschungszentrum Jülich	http://www.ptj.de/	Germany	Dr Stefan Rauschen	s.rauschen@fz-juelich.de			
31	Forschungszentrum Jülich	http://www.ptj.de/	Germany	Dr Nicolas Villacorta	n.villacorta@fz-juelich.de			
32	Forschungszentrum Jülich	http://www.ptj.de/	Germany	Dr Christiane Kummer	c.kummer@fz-juelich.de			
33	Forschungszentrum Jülich	http://www.ptj.de/	Germany	Dr Jill Ebert	j.ebert@fz-juelich.de			
34	PT-DLR	http://www.nks-lebenswissenschaften.de/	Germany	Anuscheh Vahabzadeh	anuscheh.vahabzadeh@dlr.de			
35	PT-DLR	http://www.nks-lebenswissenschaften.de/	Germany	Jan Skriwanek	jan.skriwanek@dlr.de			
36	PT-DLR	http://www.nks-lebenswissenschaften.de/	Germany	Dr Doris Bell	doris.bell@dlr.de			
37	PT-DLR	http://www.nks-lebenswissenschaften.de/	Germany	Dr Caroline Tox	caroline.tox@dlr.de			
38	VDIVDE-IT	http://www.nks-mtidw.de/	Germany	Axel Sigmund	axel.sigmund@vdivde-it.de			

	A	B	C	D	E	F
	Name	Country	Organization	E-mail		
2	Hicham Abghay	Germany	Steinbeis- Europa-Zentrum	abghay@steinbeis-europa.de		
3	Beatriz Pérez	Spain	Fundación Parque Científico De Madrid	transferencia.tecnologia@fpcm.es		
4	Lada Benzon	Croatia	Business Innovation Croatian Agency	lada.benzon@hamagbicro.hr		
5	Michael Brown	UK	Coventry University Enterprises Ltd	mike.brown@coventry.ac.uk		
6	Juan-J. Carmona-Schneider	Germany	Zenit Zentrum Für Innovation Und Technik Nordrhein-Westfalen - See more at: http://ee	jc@zenit.de		
7	Christophe Coppens	Belgium	Agence Bruxelloise Pour L'Entreprise	cco@abe.irisnet.be		
8	Georges De Lacoste	Belgium	Centre D'Accompagnement De Projets Innovants	georges.delacoste@capinnove.be		
9	María Fernández Santa Cruz Campos	Spain	Agencia Andaluza del Conocimiento	maria.fernandezsantacruz@juntadeandalucia.es		
10	Thomas Gatz	Germany	Agentur Für Innovationsförderung Und Technologietransfer Gmbh Leipzig - See more at:	gatz@agil-leipzig.de		
11	Stellan Granström	Sweden	ACREO SWEDISH ICT AB	stellan.granstrom@acreo.se		
12	Aykut Gulalanlar	Turkey	Ege University	aykut.gulalanlar@ebiltem.ege.edu.tr		
13	Vera Güth-Strasburger	Germany	European Research and Project Office GmbH	v.gueth-strasburger@eurice.eu		
14	Hendrik Pavel	UK	Exemplas Holdings Limited	h.pavel@eeneast.org.uk		
15	Helga Ilchmann	Germany	Tti Technologietransfer Und Innovationsförderung Magdeburg Gmbh - See more at: http://ee	eenpost@tti-md.de		
16	Wolfgang Korek	Germany	Berlin Partner für Wirtschaft and Technologie GmbH	wolfgang.korek@berlin-partner.de		
17	James Lambert	UK	University of Greenwich	j.lambert@gre.ac.uk		
18	Gunnar Matthiesen	Belgium	Executive Agency for Small and Medium Enterprises	gunnar.matthiesen@ec.europa.eu		
19	Marjeta Maurer	Slovenia	Centre For Interdisciplinary And Multidisciplinary Research And Studies Of The Univers	marjeta.maurer@uni-mb.si		
20	Helena Moura	Portugal	Instituto De Apoio Às Pme E À Inovação	helena.moura@iapmei.pt		
21	Paul O' Collins	UK	GWE Business West	paul.ocollins@enterpriseeuropesw.org.uk		
22	Kjeld B. Olesen	Denmark	Aalborg Municipality / North Denmark Eu-Office	kbo@aalborg.be		
23	Andreas Papadopoulos	Cyprus	Research promotion foundation	apapadopoulos@research.org.cy		
24	Christina Pascual	Greece	National Documentation Centre / National Hellenic Research Foundation - See more at:	cpascual@ekt.gr		
25	Isabelle POTTIER	France	Chambre De Commerce Et D'Industrie De Paris	ipottier@cci-paris-idf.fr		
26	Ingrid Relou	Netherlands	Stichting Syntens, Innovatienetwerk Voor Ondernemers - See more at: http://een.ec.eu	ingrid.relou@kvk.nl		
27	Fatih Sarac	Turkey	Samsun Chamber of Commerce and Industry	fsarac@samsuntso.org.tr		
28	Éva Skultéti	Hungary	Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Hajdú-Bihar County - See more at: http://een.ec	skulteti.eva@hbkik.hu		

Figure 17: Snapshots of the “Dissemination lists” excel book

ANNEX 5 - List of dissemination activities (template)

Figure 18 below depicts the “List of dissemination activities” excel book, where all partners fill in the various types of dissemination activities that they are implementing i.e. organisation of a conference, organisation of a workshop, press release, non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications), exhibition, flyers, training, social media, web-site, communication campaign (e.g radio, TV), participation to a conference, participation to a workshop, participation to an event other than a conference or workshop, video/film, brokerage event, pitch event, trade fair, participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s), other.

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CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
#	Type of activity	Partner	Title	Date	Place	Type of audience	Size of audience	Countries addressed	Comments
1	Participation to a conference	UPC	Supercomputing meeting	13-Jan-16	Universidad de las Americas, Cholula, Mexico	Scientific community (higher education, research)	50	México	
2	Participation to a conference	UPC	Supercomputing meeting		Universidad Benemérita Autónoma de Puebla	Scientific community (higher education, research)	35	México	
3	Participation to a conference	UPC	Catalan Digital Health Ecosystem - Mobile World		24-Feb-16	Mobile world Congress, Barcelona	Industry	30	Several
4	Flyers	UHULL	Dementia Awareness Day	18-May-16	Princes Quay Shopping Centre, Hull, UK, Hull, UK	Scientific community (higher education, research) General public	100 100	UK	
5	Participation to a conference	CHU-ROUEN	meeting of the Norman Gerontology Society	10-Jun-16	Unicaen, Caen	Scientific community (higher education, research)	100	France	and flyers distribution
6	Other	UPC	presentation in Bilateral Meeting on the Umbrella	4-Mar-16	Fundació Orienta, Sant Boi de Llobregat	Scientific community (higher education, research)	3	Spain	
7	Other	UPC	presentation in Bilateral Meeting on the Umbrella	3-Jun-16	Hospital Benito Menni, Sant Boi de Llobregat	Scientific community (higher education, research)	4	Spain	
8	Other	MobilesDynamics	publication of International Congress on support for dementia at a tri-mer-regional conference	21-Jun-16	CIMA white book (http://www.cima2015.com)	Policy makers	1000	France + French speaking countries	
9	Organisation of a workshop	COOSS	"Strategie Assistenziali per la non-autosufficienza" (Care Strategies for non self-sufficient people)	20-21/05/2016	Hotel Federico II, Jesi, Italy	Scientific community (higher education, research) Policy makers General public	81 20 30	Italy	Poster presented, PPT and flyers distribution
10	Social media	UHULL	Facebook page for: CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD project	23-May-16	Hull, UK	General public		UK	
11	Social media	UHULL	Twitter account for CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD-UK	12-May-16	Hull, UK	General public		UK	
12	Web-site	UHULL	http://www2.hull.ac.uk/researchandinnovation/	24-May-16	Hull, UK	Scientific community (higher education, research)		UK	
13	Other	UHULL	Interview with Caregiver	9-Jun-16	Hull, UK	General public	1	UK	
14	Other	UHULL	Interview with PwD	9-Jun-16	Hull, UK	General public	1	UK	
15	Other	UHULL	Interview with Caregiver	9-Jun-16	Hull, UK	General public	1	UK	
16	Other	UHULL	Interview with PwD	15-Jun-16	Hull, UK	General public	1	UK	
17	Other	UHULL	Interview with Caregiver	15-Jun-16	Hull, UK	General public	1	UK	
18	Other	UHULL	Interview with Healthcare Professional	23-Jun-16	Hull, UK	General public	1	UK	
19	Other	UHULL	Interview with PwD	29-Jun-16	Hull, UK	General public	1	UK	
20	Other	UHULL	Interview with Caregiver	29-Jun-16	Hull, UK	General public	1	UK	
21	Participation to a workshop	UHULL	Expert meeting on assistive technologies and dementia	05/07/16 - 06/07/16	Huddersfield, UK	Scientific community (higher education, research)	15	UK	
23	Participation in activities organised jointly with	UPC	Salut, canvi demogràfic i benestar. H2020-SC1. Ev	7-Sep-16	Universitat de Barcelona, Barcelona	Scientific community (higher education, research)	50	Spain	PPT
24	Participation to an event other than a conference	UHULL	Alzheimer's Society Memory walk (Humber Bridge)	12-Sep-16	Hull, UK	General public	1500	UK	flyers distribution
25	Participation to a conference	UHULL	26th Annual Conference of Alzheimer Europe	31/10/16-2/11/16	Copenhagen	Scientific community (higher education, research)	700	EU	Oral presentation + 3 Poster Presentations
26	Participation to an event other than a conference	UHULL	Intermed Annual meeting during 26th Annual Conference	31-Oct-16	Copenhagen	Scientific community (higher education, research)	80	EU	2 Oral presentations
27	Web-site	UHULL	Which me am I today? Blog: https://whichmeam.com	24-Nov-16	UK	Civil society			
28	Other	COOSS	Working meeting with neuropsychiatrist (Dr Scar	9-Jun-16	Ancona	Scientific community (higher education, research)			CGP presentation and commitment to present results
29	Other	COOSS	EIP-AHA	14-Apr-16	EIP-AHA EU-portal	Scientific community (higher education, research)		EU	
30	Participation to a workshop	COOSS	EIP-AHA	15-Nov-16	Bruxelles	Scientific community (higher education, research)	30	EU	
31	Participation to a workshop	COOSS	European Summit on Digital Innovation for Active	06-07-Dec-16	Bruxelles	Scientific community (higher education, research)			
32	Other	FUB	Presentation of Caregiverspro_MMD platform to	12-May-16	Hospital Sant Andreu, Manresa	General public	50	Spain	Sociosanitary Foundation of Manresa (FSSM) + Association
33	Other	FUB	Presentation of Caregiverspro_MMD platform to	24-May-16	AFABBS, Manresa	General public	30	Spain	Jointly with Association of Relatives of Alzheimer's and
34	Other	FUB	Presentation of Caregiverspro_MMD platform to	6-Jun-16	Hospital Sant Andreu, Manresa	General public	20	Spain	Addressed to Social Workers of Sociosanitary Foundation of
35	Other	FUB	Presentation of Caregiverspro_MMD platform to	8-Jun-16	Hospital Sant Andreu, Manresa	General public	30	Spain	Addressed Professional Caregivers
36	Other	FUB	Presentation of Caregiverspro_MMD platform to	10-Jun-16	Hospital Sant Andreu, Manresa	General public	30	Spain	Addressed to Dementia Unit of Central Catalonia of Soci
37	Other	FUB	Presentation of Caregiverspro_MMD platform to	21-Jun-16	Hospital Sant Andreu, Manresa	General public	20	Spain	Addressed to Assistencial Dementia Unit of Central Cata
38	Other	FUB	Presentation of Caregiverspro_MMD platform to	19-Jul-16	AFABBS, Manresa	General public	30	Spain	Addressed to Professional Caregivers of Association of R
39	Participation to a conference	FUB	R&D Health and Social: Presentation of Caregivers	29-Sep-16	Vic	General public	200	Spain	
40	Participation to a conference	FUB	R&D Health and Social: Presentation of Caregivers	30-Sep-16	Vic	General public	250	Spain	
41	Participation to a conference	FUB	Presentation of Caregiverspro_MMD platform to	30-Nov-16	Hospital Sant Andreu, Manresa	General public	100	Spain	Scientific conferences of Sociosanitary Foundation of M
42	Other	CHU-ROUEN	presentation to the medical commission of CHU	22-Feb	CHU	Scientific community (higher education, research)	57	France	
43	Other	CHU-ROUEN	presentation to the "conseil de surveillance" or s	12-Apr	CHU	Policy makers	19	France	

Figure 18: Snapshot of the "List of dissemination activities" excel book

ANNEX 6 - List of publications (template)

Figure 19 depicts the “List of publication” excel book template, where all partner’s fill in the project’s scientific publications (i.e. peer reviewed publication, paper in proceedings of a conference/workshop, article/section in an edited book or book series, thesis/dissertation, University publication/scientific monograph).

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Publication type	D.O.I.	Title	Authors	Proceedings	Date of publication	Start date of conference/ workshop	Publisher	Publisher location	ISBN	URL	Relevant pages	Open access
Peer reviewed publication	10.13053/Cys-21-1-2580	CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD: community services, helping patients with dementia and caregivers connect with others for evaluation, support and to improve the care experience	Barrué C., Cortés A., Cortés U., Tétard F., Gironès X.	Computacion y Sistemas	2017		Cic	México	ISSN 2007-9737	http://www.cys.cic.inm.mx/cis/index.php/Cys/article/view/2580/2235		Yes
Peer reviewed publication		Agents as social actors: integrating a Multi-Agent System to mediate in a social network for elder population	Barrué C., Cortés A., Cortés U.	Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Smart E	submitted							
Peer reviewed publication		How Gamification works for Health Behavior Change Support Systems: A Systematic Review	Paliokas I., Votis K., Tzovaras D.	Computer in Human Behaviour	submitted							
Peer reviewed publication		Language as a marker in subjective memory complaints screening: A sensitivity and specificity report	Segkouli S., Paliokas I., Tzovaras D., Karagiannidis, Tsolaki M.	Aging and Mental Health	submitted							
Peer reviewed publication		Web-based interventions for caregivers of people with dementia: A systematic review of the factors influencing their effectiveness	Zafeiridi P., Wolverson E., Paulson K., Dunn R., White C.	International Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry	submitted							
Peer reviewed publication		Evaluating the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD platform for supporting people with memory problems and caregivers: A usability study	Zafeiridi P., Paulson K., Wolverson E., White C., Dunn R., Antomarini M., Cortés U., Barrué C., Paliokas I., Gironès García X.,	Research protocols	in progress							
Paper in proceedings of a conference/ workshop		CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD: A European platform to support people living with dementia and their caregivers	Zafeiridi P., Dunn R., Wolverson E., Paulson K.	26th Annual Conference of Alzheimer Europ	2016	31/10/16 – 02/11/16		Copenhagen		http://www.alzheimer-europe.org/Conferences/Previous-conferences/2016-Copenhagen/Detailed-programme-and-abstracts/P14-Care-costs-and-care-financing		Yes
Paper in proceedings of a conference/ workshop		Effectiveness of technology-based interventions for People with Dementia (PwD)	Zafeiridi P., Dunn R., Wolverson E., Paulson K.	26th Annual Conference of Alzheimer Europ	2016	31/10/16 – 02/11/16		Copenhagen		http://www.alzheimer-europe.org/Conferences/Previous-conferences/2016-Copenhagen/Detailed-programme-and-abstracts/PO3-Innovative-care		Yes
Paper in proceedings of a conference/ workshop		Consulting end-users in the design and usability of CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD: An internet based support tool designed for people with dementia and their caregivers	Dunn R., Zafeiridi P., Wolverson E., Paulson K.	26th Annual Conference of Alzheimer Europ	2016	31/10/16 – 02/11/16		Copenhagen		http://www.alzheimer-europe.org/Conferences/Previous-conferences/2016-Copenhagen/Detailed-programme-and-abstracts/PO3-Innovative-care		No
Paper in proceedings of a conference/ workshop		The effectiveness of web-based interventions on dementia caregivers	Dunn R., Zafeiridi P., Wolverson E., Paulson K.	26th Annual Conference of Alzheimer Europ	2016	31/10/16 – 02/11/16		Copenhagen		http://www.alzheimer-europe.org/Conferences/Previous-conferences/2016-Copenhagen/Detailed-programme-and-abstracts/PO3-Innovative-care		Yes
Paper in proceedings of a conference/ workshop		Usability study of a web-based intervention to support people living with dementia (PLWD) and their caregivers	Zafeiridi P., Dunn R., Paulson K., Wolverson E., White C. and CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD	32 nd International Conference of Alzheim	2017	26-29 April 2017		Kyoto, Japan		http://www.adl2017.org/docs/default-source/default-document-library/adl_kyoto2017_englishabstractbook_online.pdf?sfvrsn=0	104	Yes
Paper in proceedings of a conference/ workshop		Developing a web-based platform for people living with dementia and their caregivers: A user-participatory study.	Zafeiridi P., Dunn R., Paulson K., Wolverson E., White C. and CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD	32 nd International Conference of Alzheim	2017	26-29 April 2017		Kyoto, Japan		http://www.adl2017.org/docs/default-source/default-document-library/adl_kyoto2017_englishabstractbook_online.pdf?sfvrsn=0	634	Yes
Paper in proceedings of a conference/ workshop	10.1186/ISRCTN15654731	Evaluation of benefits of the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD platform giving support and assistance to people living with dementia and their primary caregiver.	Catena, J., Rovira, E., Pardo, C., Martinez, M., Riera, C., Quintana, M., Ruiz, J., Girones, X.	23rd National Congress of the Spanish Psych	2017	23 – 25 February 2017		Bilbao, Spain				

Figure 19: Snapshot of “List of publication” excel book

ANNEX 7 - EU requirements on dissemination of results (as set in Grant Agreement)

Any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic), must:

- Display the EU emblem with appropriate prominence
- Include the following text: *“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 690211”*

In applications for protecting results (including patent applications), the following text must be included: *“The project leading to this application has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 690211”*

In reports and deliverables of public dissemination level, the following disclaimer must also be included: *“The current report reflects only the author’s view and the CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD CONSORTIUM and the Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains”*

Each beneficiary must ensure Open Access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. In particular, it must:

- As soon as possible and at latest on publication, deposit a machine readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications
- Ensure Open Access to the deposited publication –via the repository- at the latest:
 - i) on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher or
 - ii) within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in social sciences and humanities) in any other case
- Ensure Open Access –via the repository- to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- the terms European Union (EU) and Horizon 2020,
- the name of the project, acronym and grant number,
- the publication date, and length of embargo period (if any), and
- a persistent identifier.

ANNEX 8 - Guidelines for partners reporting participation in external events

Partners participating in external events (exhibitions, business events, information days, scientific events and conferences, *etc.*) should comply with the following:

- Before the event, please complete “Dissemination list.xls” (sheet «Future Events») with the required information about the event.
- If you are going to make a presentation, please use the general project presentation and make any modifications necessary to this file, keeping the same template.
- During the event, please use the project dissemination material (leaflets, posters *etc.*).
- Please do not forget to take photos.
- Update the Dissemination Leader (Q-PLAN) with your participation in the event and share the photos taken, not later than ten days after the event.
- Please complete “Dissemination activities.xls” with all required information about your participation in the event at the latest three weeks after the event.

ANNEX 9 - Event's report (template)

Figure 20 presents the event's report template that the partners are required to fill in with the necessary information after the organization of an event within the project's activities.

The figure displays two pages of an event report template. The left page is the front cover, and the right page is the data entry form.

Front Page (Left):

- Logo of the European Union.
- CAREGIVERSPRO MMD logo.
- EVENT REPORT title.
- Logos of project partners: UNIVERSITAT POLITÈCNICA DE CATALUNYA (UPC), COOSS, Mobiler Dynamic, UNIVERSITY OF Hull, Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL, and CHU Hôpital de Rouen.
- Text at the bottom: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 680211".

Data Entry Form (Right):

Event's report

Project Number	680211	Acronym	CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD
Full title	Self-management interventions and mutual assistance community services, helping patients with dementia and caregivers connect with others for evaluation, support and inspiration to improve the care experience		
Project coordinator	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya- BarcelonaTech Prof. Mises Cortés, la@ci.upc.edu		
Project URL	http://www.caregiversprommd-project.eu		

Authors (Partner)

Author1 (Partner1), Author2 (Partner2),	
Author 1	Email
Partner	Phone

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Event's report

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1 Event Aggregate Data

Title	
Date	
Venue	
Audience (number and type)	
Duration	

2 Structure of the event (short minutes)

texttexttext

3 Evaluation of the event

texttexttext

4 ANNEXES

4.1 Agenda

4.2 List of participants (names and signatures if possible)

4.3 Photos¹

4.4 Presentations

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¹ In case of photos of persons participating in pilots of CAREGIVERSPRO-MMD, their appropriate consent for publishing their photos must first be asked.

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Figure 20: Event's report template